

Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium with 2 : 2'-Diamino-Diphenyl-Disulphide in Strong Acid Solution

S. P. BAG, AMARJYOTI BASU and A. B. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 082

Manuscript received 16 January 1981, revised 18 December 1981, accepted 11 March 1982

Vanadium(V) forms a 1 : 1 (M : R) cornflower blue complex with 2 : 2'-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide in 18 N sulphuric acid solutions, which passes on to 1 : 2 (M : R) complex with larger amounts of reagents. The absorption maxima of the complexes are 590 nm and 700 nm, respectively. The colour system obeys Beer's law from 8 to 36 ppm with optimum concentration range being the same for vanadium. The percent relative error is 2.72. The compositions of the complexes were determined by the modified Job's and molar ratio methods. The calculated dissociation constants are 1.6×10^{-2} and 5×10^{-9} at 25°. The molar extinction coefficient is 1100 while the Sandell's sensitivity is $0.046 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Vanadium can be determined in the presence of large excess of foreign ions, both cations and anions.

DISODIUM maleonitrile dithiolate reacts with vanadium in 0.05 N H_2SO_4 to give an intense colour reaction but this method requires that vanadium should be present in tetravalent state¹. In 10% hydrochloric acid solution vanadium(V) can be determined with 1-naphthylamine, but the colour reaction is not very sensitive, also iron(III) and molybdenum(VI) interfere in the reaction². Acid vanadate solution reacts with 3 : 3'-diamino benzidine but the colour reaction is hindered by anions like phosphate, citrate or fluoride³.

Vanadox, 2 : 2'-imino-dibenzoic acid reacts with vanadium(V) in concentrated sulphuric acid medium⁴ to form a coloured complex. The author has listed certain reagents which may be used for estimation of vanadium(V) but none of them has been applied in determination of vanadium from complex mixtures such as alloys or ores.

The present paper describes mixed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : R) complex formation of vanadium(V) with 2 : 2'-diamino-diphenyl-disulphide in 18 N H_2SO_4 . Vanadium can be determined in alloys and ores as large number of cations, anions and masking agents such as fluoride, citrate, oxalate and EDTA do not interfere in the determination.

Experimental

Apparatus, reagents and solutions : Optical densities of the solutions were measured in 1 cm quartz cells in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer.

Preparation of O:O'-diamino-bisphenyl-disulphide⁵ : Ortho-aminobenzene thiol (0.1 mole) was dissolved in 50% EtOH and air was passed through the solution in small bubbles for 72 hr. The solution, with some suspended solid, reagent, was freed from alcohol and cooled when crystals of reagent appeared. This was filtered, washed with water and dried by suction. The product was crystallised from 90% EtOH, m.p. 65°. Analysis : Found : C, 57.95 ;

H, 4.75 ; N, 11.02. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$; C, 58.06 ; H, 4.83 ; N, 11.29%.

A 2% (w/v) reagent solution was prepared in acetonitrile (Riedel de Haen).

A standard vanadium(V) solution was made by dissolving known weight of preheated ammonium vanadate in dilute ammonium hydroxide solution. The vanadium content was checked by titration with EDTA by complexometric method⁶. Weaker solutions were obtained by proper dilution.

Sulphuric acid solution, 18 N, was prepared by diluting in 1 : 1 proportion, analytical grade conc. sulphuric acid with twice distilled water.

Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the metal salts or from the sodium or potassium salts of anions in twice distilled water and estimated according to standard methods.

Results and Discussion

Spectral transmittancy curve : 400 μg of vanadium(V) was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and 5 ml of 18 N H_2SO_4 solution and 5 ml of 2% reagent solution were added to it. The mixture was warmed on water bath for 10 min. It was cooled to room temperature and the volume was made up with 18 N sulphuric acid solution. A reagent blank was identically made in which the metal solution was not added. Absorbances of the reagent and the test solutions with water blank and of the test solution with reagent blank were taken. The curve in Fig. 1 shows that the deep blue coloured complex of vanadium and the reagent has absorption maxima at 590 nm and 700 nm.

Effect of acid concentration : To study the effect of acid concentrations, different amounts of 18 N sulphuric acid solution were added, to maintain desired acid concentrations, to 400 μg portions of vanadium(V) along with 5 ml portions of reagent.

Fig. 1. Spectral transmittancy curve.

Fig. 2

Each mixture was heated on water bath, cooled and volume made up with sulphuric acid solutions of the desired normality. Absorbance measurements of these different solutions show that the absorbances of the colour system at 590 nm increased upto an acidity of 12 N and remained constant with higher acid concentrations. All subsequent measurements were made in an optimum acid concentration of 18 N.

Effect of reagent: The absorbances of the colour system increased with the addition of increasing amounts of 2% reagent solution upto 3.0 ml. It remained constant upto 5.0 ml reagent solution in the mixture.

Effect of time: The vanadium-disulphide colour system in 18 N H_2SO_4 is stable for 24 hr; light blue crystals appear thereafter and absorbances decrease rapidly.

Beer's law, optimum range and accuracy: Beer's law is obeyed by the colour system for 8.0 to 36.0 ppm of vanadium.

The optimum range for accurate determination of vanadium was obtained by plotting percent absorbancy at 590 nm against log concentration according to Ringbom¹⁰. Fig. 2 shows that the steepest portion of the curve is from 8.0 ppm to 36 ppm of vanadium which is the optimum range; the percent relative error per 1% absolute photometric error for this range is 2.72% as obtained according to Ayres¹¹.

Sensitivity and molar extinction coefficient: Spectrophotometric sensitivity was calculated according to Sandell¹² from Beer's law curve and found to be 0.46 μg vanadium(V)/ cm^2 where the molar extinction coefficient with the disulphide is 1100.

Effect of diverse ions: Solutions of varying concentrations of foreign ions were mixed with 400

μg of vanadium(V) solutions and the colour was developed as given in the procedure. It was found that large excess (800 μg) of lithium, magnesium, calcium, ammonium, rare-earths, aluminium, titanium(IV), zirconium, thorium, iron(II and III), molybdenum(VI), tungsten(VI), platinum(IV), rhodium(III), iridium(III) and common anions like chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, phosphate, arsenate, fluoride, oxalate and citrate had no effect on the determination of vanadium. Longer period of heating is necessary for full colour development when borate is present. Copper, nickel, cobalt, palladium(II) and tartrate interfere.

Composition of the complex: It was found that the metal combines with the reagent in a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 1 which passes on to the ratio of 1 : 2 (M : R) with excess of reagent. This was found out by the modified method of Job¹³. Equimolar solutions of vanadium and the reagent were taken. Complimentary mixtures of vanadium and reagent solutions were mixed in different flasks and colour was developed. Their absorbances were measured against water as blank. The portion of extended scale of the plot in the Fig. 3 shows that vanadium combines with ligand in a ratio of 1 : 2 and rest of the portion show that vanadium also combines with the reagent in 1 : 1 ratio.

The above observations were confirmed by the molar ratio method⁷. A constant concentration of vanadium was mixed with different volumes of reagent to maintain the ratios of metal to reagent different in each study. The curve in Fig. 4 show breaks at the molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : R).

Degree of dissociation or instability constant: The degrees of dissociation, α_1 and α_2 , obtained by the method of Harvey and Manning¹⁴ are, 0.179 and 0.042, respectively, for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The dissociation constants were calculated according

Fig. 3. Job's method of composition.

Fig. 4. Molar-ratio method of composition.

to the equation, $K = \frac{(m \alpha C)^m (n \alpha C)^n}{C(1-\alpha)}$, where m

and n are the numbers of metal ions and ligand molecules involved in the complex formation, C is the molar concentration and α is the degree of

dissociation, given by $\alpha = \frac{A_m - A_s}{A_m}$; where A_m is

the absorbance with large excess of reagent and A_s is the same with stoichiometric amount of reagent in the complex. The dissociation constants at 25° are 1.6×10^{-3} for 1 : 1 complex and 5×10^{-9} for the complex with metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2.

Estimation of vanadium in alloy and ore : High-speed steel, BAS 646, 0.5 g was taken in a beaker and digested with 20 ml of 1 : 4 sulphuric acid.

When the sample dissolved, 5 ml of concentrated nitric acid was added and heated to medium-strong fumes of SO_3 . The mass was cooled and diluted with double-distilled water and oxidised with a few drops of 0.1 N KMnO_4 solution in cold. The product was stirred with excess NaOH solution (15% w/v) and boiled for a few minutes. Residue of Fe(III), Ti and Mn hydroxides and oxide was filtered off and washed with hot water. The filtrate was collected and the residue was dissolved in hot HCl (1 : 2) and reprecipitated as before. The combined filtrates were made upto 100 ml in a volumetric flask with twice distilled water. An aliquot was taken for spectrophotometric analysis. The result is given in Table 1.

Titaniferrous magnetite (magnetite+ilmenite natural mixture) ore, ground to 200 mesh was mixed with 10-12 times its weight of anhydrous sodium carbonate and a little of potassium nitrate. The mixture was fused in a platinum crucible and was kept in the fused state for 15 min. It was cooled and leached in 50 ml hot water. The product was boiled to precipitate all the hydroxides and the residue was filtered. The filtrate was finally made upto 100 ml in a volumetric flask. An aliquot was taken for the analysis of vanadium. The result is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STATISTICAL AVERAGE OF THREE READINGS FOR EACH SAMPLE

Sample	% Vanadium as certified	% Vanadium found
1. High Speed steel BAS 646	1.99	1.965
2. Titaniferrous magnetite ore	1.05	1.019

References

1. A. B. CHATTERJEE, A. BASU and S. P. BAG, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1974, 275.
2. F. M. ALBERT and M. STOIA, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1964, **202**, 420.
3. K. L. OHNG, *Talanta*, 1961, **8**, 658.
4. N. S. FRUMINA, I. S. MUSTAFIN, M. L. NIKURASHINA and M. K. VECHERA, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 138.
5. P. JOB, *Compt. Rend. Acad. Sci., Paris*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Chim. Analytique*, 1928, **9**, 113.
6. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
7. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Analyt. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
8. HOFFMAN, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2260.
9. J. KINNUNEN and B. WENNERSTRAND, *Chemist-Analyst*, 1955, **44**, 83.
10. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1938/39, **115**, 332.
11. G. H. AYRES, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 652.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 84.
13. J. R. HARVEY, JR. and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.